

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS OF 1-[4-(1-ALAMANTYL) PHENYL]-4-ACETYL-5-METHYL-1,2,3-TRIAZOLE - A NEW REAGENT FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF HYBRIDS

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Abstract

The discovery of single-molecule therapeutics capable of simultaneously combating antibiotic resistance and neurodegenerative diseases represents a critical unresolved challenge in modern medicinal chemistry. This paper describes an efficient synthesis of a new 1-adamantyl-containing reagent for the preparation of various 1,2,3-triazole hybrids as bioactive agents with dual targets. 1,2,3-Triazole-based hybrids represent a versatile and previously understudied structural class for the development of dual-target drugs, and demonstrate significant potential for further optimisation in the development of comprehensive therapeutic strategies against antibiotic-resistant infections and neurodegenerative diseases.

Keywords 1,2,3-triazol, multicomponent reaction synthesis, antimicrobial activity, 1-adamantyl.

Introduction

Antibacterial resistance has become one of the most serious global health threats, significantly reducing the effectiveness of conventional antibiotic therapy. Among resistant pathogens, *Staphylococcus aureus* is a leading cause of both community-acquired and hospital-acquired infections. In particular, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains have developed resistance to multiple β -lactam antibiotics, making treatment increasingly difficult and contributing to higher morbidity and mortality rates. Therefore, the identification and development of novel antibacterial agents effective against both methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) and MRSA remain an urgent priority in antimicrobial drug discovery [1,2].

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive and irreversible neurodegenerative disorder that represents a major global public health challenge associated with population aging.

In recent years, heterocyclic compounds have attracted considerable attention in drug discovery due to their structural diversity and broad spectrum of biological activities [3]. Among them, triazole derivatives have emerged as particularly valuable scaffolds in medicinal chemistry [4]. These compounds exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties, including anticancer [5], antitubercular [6], antiviral [7], anti-inflammatory [8], antimicrobial [9], and anti-Alzheimer activities [10]. Their versatility is attributed to their unique physicochemical properties and their ability to interact effectively with biological macromolecules [11].

An important strategy in modern medicinal chemistry involves the design of hybrid molecules that combine two or more biologically active pharmacophores within a single molecular framework. Such a hybridization approach can enhance biological activity, improve selectivity, and reduce toxicity by exploiting synergistic interactions between different structural motifs. Numerous studies have demonstrated that hybrid compounds containing a 1,2,3-triazole scaffold often exhibit significantly enhanced biological activity compared with their parent structures.

Materials and Methods

Instruments and Chemicals

All chemicals and solvents used in the experimental procedures were purchased commercially from Aldrich or Merck and were used without further purification unless otherwise specified. Melting points (m.p.) were determined using an Electrothermal 9100 capillary melting point apparatus and are reported uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} using a PerkinElmer 55148 Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectrometer. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained in DMSO-d_6 or CDCl_3 using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard on a Bruker 600 MHz NMR spectrometer. Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Thermo Flash 2000 organic elemental analyzer (CHN). Absorbance measurements were carried out at 517 nm using a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1-[4-(1-adamantylphenyl)]-4-acetyl-5-methyl-1,2,3-triazoles (2)

Synthesis of 1-[4-(1-adamantylphenyl)]-4-acetyl-5-methyl-1,2,3-triazole (2)

A 100 mL two-neck round-bottom flask was charged with p-substituted aniline (10 mmol) and sodium carbonate (5 mmol), and the mixture was stirred in an ice bath. Separately, NaNO_2 (10 mmol) was dissolved in 2 mL of distilled water, while concentrated HCl (2 mL) was mixed with 2 mL of distilled water. This solution was added dropwise to the reaction flask while carefully maintaining the temperature to prevent a rapid increase. Sodium azide (NaN_3 , 10 mmol) was then added, and the reaction mixture was allowed to warm spontaneously to room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ\text{C}$). After reaching the desired temperature, acetylacetone (10 mmol), potassium carbonate (15 mmol), and 15 mL of ethanol were added, and the mixture was refluxed for 1–4 h (Scheme 1). The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC). Upon completion, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into an ice–water mixture with stirring. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water, and recrystallized from absolute ethanol.

Yellowish solid; mp $122\text{--}124^\circ\text{C}$; yield: 3.35 g (quantitative); $R_f = 0.46$ (n-hexane/ethyl acetate, 2:3); IR (KBr): 1689 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching), 1509 cm^{-1} (N=N stretching), 3044 cm^{-1} (aromatic C–H stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, DMSO-d_6): δ 7.45 (d, $J = 12.0\text{ Hz}$, 2H, Ar–H), 7.01 (d, $J = 12.0\text{ Hz}$, 2H, Ar–H), 2.39 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.92, 1.68, 1.48 (m, 15H, Ad), 1.67 (s, 3H, CH_3); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (150 MHz, DMSO-d_6): δ 194.99 (C=O), 148.15 ($\text{H}_3\text{C-C=C-}$), 134.50 (Ar–C–N), 133.27 ($\text{H}_3\text{C-C=C-}$), 129.71 (Ar–C), 128.96 (Ar–C), 119.21 (Ar–C), 24.10 ($\text{H}_3\text{C-C=O}$), 11.13 (CH_3); Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 75.22; H, 7.46; N, 12.54. Found: C, 75.24; H, 7.43; N, 12.55.

Results and Discussion

For the synthesis of the hybrid compound, the derivative 1-[4-(1-adamantylphenyl)]-4-acetyl-5-methyl-1,2,3-triazole (2) was first obtained.

The reaction was carried out in an alkaline medium and proceeded through four stages. In the first stage, the reaction medium was alkalized with a sodium carbonate solution. In the second stage, diazotization was performed at low temperature. In the third stage, p-substituted aryl azide derivatives were prepared using

sodium azide (NaN_3). In the final stage, the 1,2,3-triazole derivative (2) was synthesized through a Knoevenagel-type reaction between acetylacetone and p-adamantyl aryl azide catalyzed by potassium carbonate. The reaction proceeded rapidly and afforded the target product in high yield.

Spectroscopic Characterization of the Synthesized Compound (2)

The structures of the synthesized 1,2,3-triazole derivatives (2) were successfully confirmed by FT-IR, $^1\text{H NMR}$, and $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ spectroscopic analyses.

In compound (2), the characteristic C=O stretching vibrations observed in the FT-IR spectra at approximately $1680\text{--}1693\text{ cm}^{-1}$ clearly indicate the presence of the acetyl group, while the absorption bands in the region of $1500\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to N=N stretching vibrations of the triazole ring.

In the $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra, aromatic protons appear as two doublets ($J \approx 9.6\text{--}12.0\text{ Hz}$), characteristic of para-disubstituted phenyl rings, confirming the structural symmetry of the molecule. Singlet signals observed at approximately δ 2.2–2.7 ppm and δ 1.6–1.7 ppm were assigned to the acetyl and triazole methyl groups, respectively.

In the $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ spectra, signals in the range of δ 189–197 ppm correspond to the carbonyl carbon atom, whereas the remaining aromatic and heterocyclic carbon atoms appear within their expected chemical shift regions.

Conclusion

In this study, 1-[4-(1-adamantylphenyl)]-4-acetyl-5-methyl-1,2,3-triazole (2) was successfully synthesized. The obtained compound may serve as a valuable intermediate for the development of hybrid pharmaceutical agents with enhanced lipophilicity due to the presence of the adamantyl substituent.

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